

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF THE INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPECIAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the didactic possibilities of the integrative approach to the development of special competencies of future technological education teachers, methods of using methods, and the system of training of specialized subjects are highlighted.

Keywords: intelligence, integration, quality, standard, technology, direction, activity

ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИНТЕГРАТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА К РАЗВИТИЮ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация: В данной статье освещены дидактические возможности интегративного подхода к развитию специальных компетенций будущих учителей технологического образования, способы использования методов, система обучения профильных предметов.

Ключевые слова: интеллект, интеграция, качество, стандарт, технология, направление, деятельность.

INTRODUCTION

Modern requirements for the educational process give us the opportunity to accept the organization and formation of professional and special competence as a pedagogical process. When evaluating the special competence of future teachers of technological education, it is necessary to pay attention to a number of integrated pedagogical conditions that help to achieve high efficiency in education.

In our republic, the issue of training intellectually competent future specialists is also of national importance, and special attention is being paid to solving this issue. In the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, further improvement of the continuous education system, increasing the possibilities of quality education services, training of highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market, and the quality of education and training the task of introducing international standards of assessment is defined. Therefore, improving the preparation of future teachers of technological education for professional activity based on an integrative approach, producing innovative methods and technologies suitable for them, as well as preparing scientific and methodical support are considered to be current trends in this field. In this regard, teachers trained taking into account the state policy in this field will become specialists who can make a worthy contribution to the intellectualization of all aspects of our country. Based on the content of the above issues, the state documents that are suitable and specific to the traditional education system will be studied first, and the ideas and instructional thoughts in them aimed at modernizing the preparation of future teachers for professional activities based on modern requirements will be discussed. are taken into account when solving the problem and their didactic possibilities are taken into account. Below we will talk about some of them:

- The existence of a qualification requirement for training future technological education teachers for professional activity

- Availability of State educational standards in the subjects related to the preparation of future technological education teachers for professional activities.
- Availability of qualification descriptions for future technological education teachers.
- Future technological education in the curriculum of the field of education, the possibility of implementing the preparation of teachers for professional activity based on an integrative approach, etc.

MAIN PART

This latter possibility suggests that a strong emphasis should be placed on integrating the professional preparation of future technology education teachers from the very beginning. Blocks of subjects in the preparation of the future teacher of technological education for professional activity have specific goals and tasks, and it is necessary to determine their adequacy to solve the problem.

The opportunities and conditions in the studied State documents are considered as the initial opportunities for training the future teacher of technological education on the basis of an integrative approach. At the same time, the results of our preliminary research in this direction show that it is possible to prepare future teachers of technological education for intellectual activity on the basis of an integrative approach. This increases the importance of training future teachers of technological education on the basis of an integrative approach, taking into account the requirements of the time, and also increases the social importance of such problems. And it can be noted that the researched problem itself can be a promising topical problem of national significance.

Therefore, at the initial stage of our research work, the pedagogical and psychological conditions of training future technological education teachers based on an integrative approach were scientifically and methodologically based. For this purpose, we scientifically and methodically based the interrelated logical sequence of the process of forming the skills and qualifications of the future teacher of technological education based on an integrative approach. We expressed them as follows:

- Formation of knowledge, skills and competencies related to integration in future teachers of technological education.
- Teaching future teachers of technological education to choose integrative directions. This is carried out during the second course of training of future technological education teachers;
- To teach future teachers of technological education to create integrative functions and to understand their goals and tasks and content. This is carried out during the third courses of training of future technological education teachers for professional activity;
- Preparing future teachers of technological education for an integrative approach. These graduate courses for professional training of future teachers of technological education are carried out in the educational process.

Didactic materials and informational materials suitable for the training of future technological education teachers mentioned above, as well as creative information environments needed to solve the problem, were prepared. On the basis of systematized data, a database will be prepared that will help to solve the problem of the formation of skills and qualifications related to the preparation of future technological teachers for professional activities based on an integrative approach. This created ample opportunities to prepare methodological bases for the formation of updated (modernized) educational content for the training of future technological education teachers. On the basis of such possibilities, it will be possible to look at the solution of the problem

of integrating the information prepared according to the solved stages into the content of the traditional educational process. For this, the rules, principles and conclusions regarding the integration of educational content were studied: Teaching tools; learning algorithm; integration of teaching content; teaching standards; teaching technologies; selection of information for teaching; integration in education; selection of features in teaching and so on. Based on the results of our research in this field, it was also possible to form a judgmental opinion about the integration of educational content. We expressed it as follows: we came to the understanding that the integration of educational content means a strong connection between the contents, the process of their transition to each other and the results corresponding to them, as well as the synthesis of knowledge in this process, an integrated system of types of activities and abilities. The psychological aspects of our research in this direction are also important, that is, integration work in the educational content educates most of the characteristics of future technological educators. The following opinion about this is important: — Education of characteristics in teaching-teaching of sciences aims to educate students' scientific attitude, attitudes characterized by the following: interest (desire to know) and activity (desire to do something to find out something) ; skepticism (willingness to scrutinize common ideas); reasoning (skills of using the logic of proof and rules in acquiring knowledge); awareness (the existence of a fund of information about the 110 world so that it is possible to think with its help); strategies (the presence of rules for searching and the desire to use them); tendency (as a result of acquiring new knowledge, the student begins to reconsider his way of thinking about the world, placing the ideas and concepts of others on the same line based on the law)

Pedagogical aspects of training future technological teachers in this area based on an integrative approach are also very important. Therefore, the pedagogical conditions for the integration of the materials related to the training of future technological education teachers based on the integrative approach into the traditional educational content were also studied. In it, the blocks of subjects in the curriculum of the training of future technological teachers are also studied, and on this basis, the information on the algorithmic stages prepared for the training of future technological teachers on the basis of an integrative approach is traditional integrated into the educational content. Taking into account the above, it can be said that the process of skill formation related to the preparation of future teachers of technological education for professional activity based on an integrative approach is solved during their entire education at the higher educational institution.

CONCLUSION

Their integration, choice of an integrative direction, implementation of an integrative function will be a propeditive and didactic supporting basis for the solution of this problem. Based on the results of our research, we found it appropriate to make the following conclusions:

- Pedagogical and psychological conditions for training future teachers of technological education based an integrative approach created ample opportunities for the development of excellent educational content based on scientific and methodological aspects in the training of teachers;
- The scope and scope of the research carried out on the four stages of training future teachers of technological education based on an integrative approach (integration; choice of an integrative direction; implementation of an integrative function; an integrative approach) are considered showed the necessity of forming a database in solving the problem;

• The large number of stages of training future technological education teachers on the basis of an integrative approach (they are four) showed that this research process and their results are regularly monitored, otherwise deviations in the research process (ineffective ways) may occur and so on.

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